

Trans Omental Hernia: A Case Report

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Abstract

We present a case of a 57-year-old male who developed a rare transomental internal hernia leading to small bowel obstruction (SBO). The patient, with no prior surgical history, presented with diffuse abdominal pain, vomiting, and obstipation. Clinical and radiological investigations, including an abdominal X-ray and CT scan, indicated a mechanical SBO with a transitional point and a beak sign.

During exploratory laparotomy, a 2.5 cm defect in the greater omentum was identified, with ileal incarceration 150 cm from the duodenojejunal junction. There was no bowel necrosis. The surgical intervention included reduction of the herniated bowel segment and partial resection of the greater omentum. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on the first postoperative day.

The article discusses the diagnostic challenges of transomental hernias due to their nonspecific clinical presentations and the importance of imaging, especially CT scans. It emphasizes the role of both laparoscopic and open surgical approaches in management. Preventive measures are recommended to avoid recurrence.

Introduction

Small bowel obstruction (SBO) is a common surgical emergency that can result from various causes. Among these, internal hernias are a rare but important cause of SBO, especially in patients without a history of abdominal surgery. Internal hernias occur when the small bowel becomes trapped within a peritoneal or mesenteric defect, leading to obstruction and potential bowel ischemia if not promptly treated.

This case report presents the diagnosis and management of presentation of a rare trans omental hernia causing a small bowel obstruction. The article discusses the diagnostic approach, and the surgical management of such hernias.

Presentation of the Case

A 57-year-old male patient, with no notable medical or surgical history, was admitted to emergency room of Ibn Rochd University hospital center for abdominal pain. Present for 4 days, the pain was diffuse, with progressively increasing intensity, accompanied by vomiting and obstipation.

Physical examination revealed an abdomen with no surgical scars, a slight abdominal distension, diffuse abdominal tenderness and tympanic sounds. The hernial orifices were clear, and the rectal examination was normal. There were no signs of peritoneal irritation.

An abdominal X-Ray revealed air-fluid levels more wide than tall. An abdominal CT scan was performed showing appearance of a mechanical small bowel obstruction upstream of a transitional point, demonstrating the beak sign (figure 1).

An exploratory laparotomy was indicated and performed, which revealed incarceration of the ileum approximately 150 cm from the duodeno-jejunal angle through a 2,5 defect in the greater omentum (figure 2A), with distension of the upstream segment, but no signs of bowel necrosis (figure 2B). These findings suggested a diagnosis of a transomental internal hernia.

More Information

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Small bowel obstruction, internal hernia, transomental hernia, Greater omentum defect, Rare internal hernia, acute intestinal obstruction.

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Figure 1: CT (Axial View) Demonstrating Mechanical SBO Upstream of a Transitional Point, Demonstrating the Beak Sign

Figure 2: Greater Omentum Defect (A) Small Bowel Distension Upstream to an Incarcerated Segment (B)

Surgical management involved the reduction of the herniated intestinal segment and a partial resection of the greater omentum.

The postoperative course was uncomplicated, and the patient was discharged home at day 1 post-operative.

Discussion

This case highlights a rare form of small bowel obstruction (SBO) due to a transomental internal hernia (TOIH), an unusual condition that can present diagnostic challenges due to its non-specific clinical and radiological features.

Internal hernias account for approximately 0.5% to 1% of all cases of bowel obstruction [1]. Among these, **transomental hernias** are particularly uncommon, constituting only about 1-4% of all internal hernias [2]. They involve both the greater and lesser omentum.

For the greater omentum, the hernia may be located either at the level of the gastrocolic ligament [3] or at the level of the omental apron. In the latter case, the defect is most often on its right side [4], with the small intestine becoming incarcerated from back to front,

positioning itself in the right paracolic gutter and pushing the colon inward [1,5].

The clinical presentation generally corresponds to a nonspecific acute bowel obstruction syndrome, primarily combining abdominal pain and vomiting. If performed, an abdominal X-ray (ASP) shows small bowel air-fluid levels, which may even suggest the diagnosis when these levels displace the stomach and project toward the lesser sac [6]. A contrast-enhanced CT scan can confirm the preoperative diagnosis [3,5,7], revealing the passage of mesenteric vessels through an omental defect [5,8]. However, since this sign is rarely sought, less than 10% of transomental hernias are diagnosed preoperatively [9].

The laparoscopic approach is advantageous, both diagnostically and therapeutically, since the defect is anterior, easy to identify, and can be repaired without difficulty [8]. However, a midline laparotomy may be immediately preferred in cases of poorly tolerated, overt bowel obstruction syndrome [1].

Intra-operative diagnosis is generally straightforward, except in the very rare cases of mixed hernias, which can significantly alter the anatomy by massively displacing the stomach forward and laterally.

Reduction is most often achieved by gentle traction on the small intestine. However, it may be complicated by adhesions between the intestine and the peritoneum lining the lesser sac. In such cases, it is preferable to widely open the lesser sac, either by incising the gastrocolic ligament or by enlarging the defect. This procedure can be easily performed laparoscopically using *LigaSure™* or *Ultracision®* to minimize the risk of thermal spread. In cases of bowel necrosis, surgical treatment follows the usual principles of resection [1]. Regardless of the defect's location, preventing recurrence involves direct closure with separate sutures of absorbable thread, followed by anatomical repositioning of the intestine and omentum [2]. However, if the omental apron appears too altered, resection is preferable (4). In our approach we preferred to perform a partial resection of the greater omentum although there were no signs of distress.

Conclusion

Internal abdominal hernias are very rare, but they should be suspected in any patient presenting with acute intestinal obstruction who has no history of surgery. These hernias typically manifest as bowel obstruction and are often confirmed during an exploratory laparotomy. Treatment is urgent and can be performed through either laparotomy or laparoscopy.

Provenance and Peer Review

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Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflicts Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exists.

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References

- [1] Masson E. EM-Consulte. Traitement chirurgical des hernies internes.
- [2] Ghahremani GG. Internal abdominal hernias. *Surg Clin North Am.* 1984 Apr;64(2):393–406.
- [3] Takagi Y, Yasuda K, Nakada T, Abe T, Matsuura H, Saji S. A case of strangulated transomental hernia diagnosed preoperatively. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 1996 Aug;91(8):1659–60.
- [4] Quénu J. Opérations sur les parois de l'abdomen et sur le tube digestif. Paris: Masson; 1967. 1248 p.
- [5] Delabrousse E, Couvreur M, Saguet O, Heyd B, Brunelle S, Kastler B. Strangulated transomental hernia: CT findings. *Abdom Imaging.* 2001;26(1):86–8.
- [6] Tran TL, Regan F, al-Kutoubi MA. Computed tomography of lesser sac hernia through the gastrohepatic omentum. *Br J Radiol.* 1991 Apr;64(760):372–4.
- [7] Okayasu K, Tamamoto F, Nakanishi A, Takanashi T, Maehara T. A case of incarcerated lesser sac hernia protruding simultaneously through both the gastrocolic and gastrohepatic omenta. *Radiat Med.* 2002;20(2):105–7.
- [8] Choong AM, Carney L, Beaconsfield T, Shorvon PJ, Bhutiani RP. 'The ins and outs of abdominal pain': a case report of a transomental internal hernia. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl.* 2010 Sep;92(6):W35–6.
- [9] Kobayashi T, Mouri T, Fujii T. A case report and literature reviews of trans-omental hernia. *Rinsho Geka.* 1994;49:1501–5.

